

Event: 2nd Conference on Research Data Infrastructure

Placeholder Session title

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Towards interoperability of DMPs among different services in Life Sciences

on the example of DMP exchange between DataPLAN and RDMO

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Abstract

Interoperability, i.e., the possibility to combine information generated in different contexts and across different platforms, is a key request in the general framework of Open Science and FAIR data [1]. This should also be done for project-related information collected in the form of Data Management Plans (DMPs). In contrast to free-text DMPs, machine-actionable DMPs (maDMPs) provide a machine-readable format that allows for automated processing and integration into different platforms.

To facilitate interoperability, the Research Data Alliance DMP Common Standards Working Group suggested a minimum set of application-independent fields for maDMPs [2]. At the same time, some DMP platforms, such as RDMO [3] and DataPLAN [4], define DMPs as structured objects composed of fine-grained fields, which allows further comparison and mapping between them and facilitates potential interoperability.

In our workgroup, we intend to implement the subsequent steps towards DMP interoperability, starting with the two platforms used in the NFDI context, RDMO and DataPLAN. Our initial task, which began at a three-day hackathon in October 2024, is aligning the given DMP data models to each other [5], similar to previous work on the alignment of software management plans [6]. In the following, we will check the capability of each software to import/export information according to one of the other data models. Our test use cases will be a generic DMP and a DMP for life sciences.

Our work will help design DMP infrastructure and templates to be interoperable from the beginning. We plan to work together with the developers of DMP platforms to extend their

functionalities and with authoritative community initiatives such as the Research Data Alliance.

We are optimistic that with this baseline, further implementations will take place, benefiting all instances and tools that rely on RDMO, the NFDI Consortia, and the wider community, allowing the extension of this work towards other disciplines and advancing towards maDMPs.

Keywords: Data management plans, DataPLAN, Machine-actionability, maDMPs, semantics, RDMO

Resources

DataPLAN - DataPLANT's tool for creating data management plans: <https://dmpg.nfdi4plants.org/>

RDMO: <https://rdmorganiser.github.io/>

DMP alignment results: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15129830>

Author contributions

JL: Conceptualization; Methodology; Writing - Original Draft; Writing – review & editing; Formal analysis; Visualization

XZ: Conceptualization; Methodology; Resources; Writing - Original Draft; Writing – review & editing; Formal analysis; Visualization

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GL: Conceptualization; Methodology; Writing - Original Draft; Writing – review & editing; Formal analysis; Visualization

Competing interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

Funding

The authors rely on the support of their respective Consortia and institutions.

X.-R. Z. and S. E. were financially supported by the NFDI consortium "DataPLANT – Daten in Pflanzen-Grundlagenforschung", funded by the German Research Foundation (DFG) under the grant Nr. 442077441 (<https://gepris.dfg.de/gepris/projekt/442077441>).

Sabine Schönau and Leyla Jael Castro are part of the DMP4NFDI service - a service part of Base4NFDI. Base4NFDI is funded by DFG, as part of [NFDI](#), under project number [521466146](#).

Leyla Jael Castro's contributions to this effort are also part of the NFDI4DataScience consortium funded by DFG under project number [460234259](#).

Acknowledgement

Part of the authors belong to the NFDI Consortia DataPLANT, NFDI4Ing, NFDI4DataScience, NFDI4Chem, NFDI4Biodiversity, to the cross-cutting workgroup Infra-DMP, to the basis services consortium DMP4NFDI, and to the RDMO community.

References

- [1] GO FAIR <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/>
- [2] 'RDA DMP Common Standard for Machine-actionable Data Management Plans'. Accessed: Mar. 17, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.15497/rda00039>
- [3] Anders, I. *et al.*, 'The Research Data Management Organiser (RDMO) – a Strong Community Behind an Established Software for DMPs and Much More', *Data Science Journal*, 2024, <https://doi.org/10.5334/dsj-2024-028>
- [4] Zhou, X.-R. *et al.*, 'DataPLAN: A Web-Based Data Management Plan Generator for the Plant Sciences', *Data*, vol. 8, no. 11, Art. no. 11, Nov. 2023, <https://doi.org/10.3390/data8110159>
- [5] Solanki, L. *et al.*, (2025). Crosswalks from the NFDI4DS hackathon "machine-actionable Data Management Plan for NFDI" [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15129830>
- [6] Castro, L. J., Gonzalez, E., Grossmann, Y. V., Solanki, D., & Utrilla, C. (2023). Metadata crosswalks for software management plans at NFDI4DS hackathon maSMP 2023 [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10275895>

Other references

DMP4NFDI <https://dmp.services.base4nfdi.de/>